

OEE CAN BE YOUR KEY

Change formula for equipment availability to improve performance

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OVERALL EQUIPMENT EFFICIENCY (OEE) MEASURES the ratio of how much of a product or part is being made defect-free versus how much could be made according to the equipment's design. A machine or process that has an OEE of 100 percent is producing at its maximum designed capacity with zero defects.

Three metrics – availability, performance and quality – make up OEE. When real output is lower than expected, practitioners can find opportunities for improvement in all three of these factors and take actions that maximize the current process capabilities, fix problems and improve productivity.

OEE availability is a time metric that usually measures as a percentage of the operating time. Machine availability is a measure of how much time this machine was available to manufacture a product or part. A machine that is busy or can't make products is considered unavailable.

Improving the machine's availability time by reducing wastes and excess motions from the process can reduce costs by a large amount. This improves the utilization and the lead-time required to make a product. The more wastes removed from the process, the less time will be needed to produce the target. Overtime and excess resource issues usually result from an improper utilization of the operating time.

Performance is one of the most debated metrics in lean. It takes into account the factors that affect the speed of the machines. Most companies take the number of pieces produced and compare it to the design, count quality and availability. Then they assume that problems with machine speed have been caused by improper maintenance. However, performance can be affected by many other factors, such as having untrained operators, poor operating instructions or no instructions at all.

Working at low speed is a waste because the machine is delivering fewer units per hour and using more resources than it needs. Some companies plan their productivity according to the current situation and the current process capability, making jobs that should take a few hours last an entire shift. Since they don't run trials to evaluate and see if the process can be improved, their processes never will run efficiently. The rule is that no process is perfect. If the process is improved, wastes are removed and the machine runs at optimum speeds, the same productivity can be achieved in less time with even fewer operators.

Quality, so important for your customers, can be one of the greatest wastes in the process. Quality is what adds value for your customer and keeps you in business. If a process produces a number of defective pieces, the required working time to compensate for those defects and reproduce sellable

items will reduce the manufacturing unit's capacity to make new products. The cost of producing a defective piece plus the cost of reworking it could be more than double the cost of making the piece right the first time. Defective products that reach the customer can lead to a complete loss of business. It is more important to make sellable parts instead of making huge quantities of parts. Reducing the defects ratio will improve the real output of the machine, increase your system's capacity to make products, reduce inspection efforts, curb costs and add value to your business.

Basic OEE calculation

Basically, any machine has a capacity. It should be able to deliver a specific number of units in a given time. If it can produce 20 units in an hour, it should produce 160 units during an eight-hour shift. Over five days, this machine's rated capacity is 800 units when everything is perfect. A machine that must slow to half speed can make only 400 units, reducing performance by half: $(800-400)/800 = 0.5$, or 50 percent.

Adding break times to the calculations could take five more hours out of a five-day week. This makes the machine's availability in a 40-hour week 87.5 percent, or $0.875 (40-5)/40$. Multiplying the availability of 0.875 by the machine's reduced capacity of 400 means that it can make only 350 units during one week.

Availability tracks the time that the machine isn't available for use. If we have 10 units that need rework because of quality defects, the quality ratio becomes $(350 - 10)/350 = 0.9714$, or 97.14 percent. Since OEE equals performance multiplied by availability multiplied by quality, we have $0.5 \times 0.875 \times 0.9714 = 42.5$ percent.

An OEE of 42.5 percent yields 340 units per week. Since world-class OEE is 85 percent, we know that something needs to be fixed.

One more thing is whether OEE calculation should be based on 24 hours a day and seven days a week or just the number of hours the machine was operated. Obviously, OEE is higher if it only considers the operating shifts. But if a factory only operates one eight-hour shift five days a week, can a machine's OEE really be 100 percent? What about the 128 hours a week the machine is not available because the factory is closed? Should the availability not be $40/168$, or 23.8 percent?

The first figure of 100 percent focuses only on the wastes during times of operation, also called operational wastes. The second number shows that 76 percent improvement is possible. If a huge order appeared, the team would know that it has 128 extra hours of availability. This time also could be used if sales improved. Both figures should be used and calculated.

WOE IS US

Figure 1. The most common availability and lost time issues in manufacturing operations.

Some organizations report a low OEE because they have problems with sales. For instance, if they have orders for only 600 pieces per shift with equipment that could produce 1,200 pieces per shift, they produce only what the customer needs. This shift's OEE is 100 percent only if the equipment is running at optimum efficiency and producing the target of 600 in four hours. Shifts under the same parameters that produce 600 pieces in eight hours have an OEE of 50 percent. In the first case, the equipment was available for the other four hours because the factory was open, but there were no orders to process. In the second case, this is the improvement that should be made to the process.

Factors affecting OEE metrics

Understanding the problem is the first step of any problem-solving technique. Analyzing it is the second step. Processes are not being measured and metrics are not being set to just realize the current condition, but to understand the current process condition to find the best way to help with improvements. After improvements have started, the metrics are used to measure progress.

To measure effectively and accurately and collect the

details needed, practitioners must understand what is being analyzed, what each metric measures or presents, and what problems the three metrics of availability, performance and quality cover.

Availability. As shown in Figure 1, availability of the machine can be affected by numerous factors. Each problem in Figure 1 presents a different type of improvement. Availability often focuses on the waste of waiting, one of the most common of the seven forms of muda. It can be seen in most process improvement events.

Unfortunately, many use availability as a measure of uptime, subtracting many other wastes, thus presenting this formula:

$$\frac{\text{Total working time (uptime + downtime)} - \text{Total downtime}}{\text{Total working time}}$$

The above formula tends to focus on the machine downtime, which often is caused by preventive maintenance, routines, adjusting, calibration, overhaul and other maintenance activities. The goal of maintenance is uptime, but just because the equipment is working does not mean it is available to make products. Numerous other factors, such as

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waiting for material or employee breaks, influence the availability of the process or machine. Counting only maintenance downtime in the availability calculation leaves practitioners trying to improve preventive maintenance or mean time to repair, meaning they could ignore improvements to the other wastes.

The main goal of OEE is to understand the obstacles and wastes that are lowering the productivity rate. For this reason, availability should be presented by this formula:

$$\frac{\text{Total production working time} - \text{Total production downtime}}{\text{Total production working time}}$$

Production downtime is a term that presents all time losses and obstacles that could prevent the machine from making a product. Performing a complete time analysis and reporting it in terms of availability along with something like a Pareto chart can help focus on the most critical issues and provide ideas about how this process is being managed.

For example, in the manufacturing process, machines that must wait for material or parts indicate a supply chain problem. Having too much work-in-process between the process steps will constrain the parts flowing through the line. However, having no inventory between the process steps could halt production if another process supplying parts shuts down unexpectedly. Adding some inventory, or adequate buffers, between processes could avoid such problems. Such inventory buffering would include a little bit of safety stock and a technique like pull cards, also known as kanban cards.

Changeover time is another example of waste. The insufficient availability of tools could result in a lot of time spent adjusting machines and processes to produce another type of product. Having the necessary tools available and reducing setup and changeover times can have dramatic results. Waiting for the operator to get tools or spare parts is a common issue in most industrial companies.

Performance. Unlike availability, the primary cause of performance issues often are hidden, as they can overlap with the availability metric. Data management programs like ERPs don't provide solutions or root causes of problems. Regardless of quality and availability, machines could have low output because of their slow speeds. Many machine speed issues are caused by poor maintenance. Better calibration, machine adjustments, tweaking the process and ensuring a solid electrical current can help resolve problems with low machine speeds.

Apart from that, companies often neglect other factors that influence process performance, including operator skills, oper-

ator training and the quality of instructions. It is hard to catch such performance problems with common data-gathering systems. The information available to determine performance includes the number of pieces produced, the actual capability, downtime and the number of defects produced. Considering availability and quality can hint at performance problems without revealing the true cause.

Quality. It is not difficult to know how many defective products are produced, as a simple sheet of paper can record this information. What is not easy to know is what caused the defects. Finding out can require intensive efforts to understand the source of variation that is causing the quality problem.

For all three of these metrics, the main goal of data gathering should not be having a perfect measurement. The goal is not to recognize the percentage of each waste. Metrics provide a feedback about how the process is running. They don't make the process details visible. It will be necessary to perform an in-depth process analysis to grasp the real situation and allow you to eliminate the root causes of the problems.

Analyzing OEE metrics to improve the process

Metrics just indicate how the process is running, but they don't provide deep analysis or understanding of why this is happening. The question now is how to analyze the process for better understanding of the current condition. At Toyota, genchi genbutsu is widely used for understanding the current condition. This is also known as gemba. This Japanese term is part of Toyota's way for developing and training its leaders to look at problems and observe the real situation, as opposed to relying on metrics and numbers. It means go and see where the work is done. A manager who monitors a process by standing beside the machine or the production line for a while or for a full working shift can see how the process is being run and managed compared to the standard. Those who manage shop floors from a distance face the problem of being out of touch. How can they know the reality of the situation if they don't see it with their own eyes?

For example, machine setup time and changeovers are direct availability problems. The common cause of this problem is a tools issue. Either insufficient tools are available at the operator's place or the tools are not handy. This forces the operator to go get the tools needed, delaying the changeover process. Likewise, the operators might lack the training to know where the appropriate tools are located, making performance an operator training issue. Operators also might not have received sufficient enough training to be familiar with

OEE FOR YOUR HEALTH

Like many tools from manufacturing and industrial engineering, OEE is finding its way into the healthcare domain, according to *Healthcare Packaging* magazine.

According to the periodical, OEE is popular because it is easy to understand and relatively easy to apply. But as with any tool, applying OEE on packaging lines – healthcare or otherwise – must be done carefully. But if a packaging line or plant aims to increase productivity by 40 percent or less, OEE can indicate current performance. Following up with lean and/or Six Sigma techniques can drive the performance.

Although OEE can be calculated with a clipboard and pen, experts told *Healthcare Packaging* that displaying real-time data to operators, combined with supporting information that lets them understand the root causes of availability, line performance or quality issues, is a better way to drive improvement.

the changeover task. Managers who take the go-and-see approach can discover real problems that the data only hint at. This is why gemba is one of the main core values of the Toyota production system.

Finding problems in quality is an important function of management. When faced with issues, many practitioners go straight to a complex tool like Six Sigma to find the sources of variation. But often, the simple approach of go and see could find the real cause easily. Monitoring how the operator is producing, revising the work against the standard, and involving the technical team could clear up many things. Comparing the machine or process with another one that produces the same part with fewer defects can make the analysis even quicker and easier.

At Toyota, managers use very few complex statistical tools for quality. They usually stick with go and see, mistake-proofing techniques, a simple analysis tool like Pareto and problem-solving approaches like the five-whys, as Jeffrey K. Liker reported in his best-selling book *The Toyota Way*.

After reviewing details about the metrics, the next question becomes which problem to work on. A Pareto analysis can give you a good start by examining each factor that influences

process efficiency. Each factor receives a weight corresponding to its effect on cost.

However, tackling the biggest problem that poses the greatest cost might not be prudent if the company's culture resists change. If managers and directors aren't on board with continuous improvement, it might be better to pick a problem that can be fixed quickly and easily. Presenting the benefits from that project's process improvement could generate the necessary support from top management to improve other processes continuously.

OEE and lean in a new light

Why are we always seeking the most efficient process with minimum wasted time and the lowest defect rate? Because it is all about the customer.

One of lean manufacturing's most important calculations is takt time, or the rate of customer demand for a group or family of products produced by one process, as presented by Mike Rother in his book *Toyota Kata*. Takt time is calculated by dividing the effective operating time of a process (be it a shift, a day, etc.) by the quantity of items that the customer requires from the process in that time period.

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For example, the operating time for a process is 25,200 seconds per shift. But the effective operating time is the operating time minus allowances, which can include planned downtime, lunches, breaks, team meetings, cleanup and planned maintenance. Unplanned downtimes, such as changeovers, are those variables that need to be improved to have the best effective operating time. If the customer demands 420 pieces of a product during an eight-hour shift, the takt time will be 25,200 divided by 420, or 60 seconds. This means that based on the available time, on average, the customer is buying one unit every 60 seconds.

Obviously, the intended cycle time of an assembly process, called planned cycle time, is usually less than the takt time. So in less than one hour, we expect this machine on this shift to produce 60 pieces of product. Any interference would reduce the productivity rate of this machine and delay the product for the customer. The OEE can present those interferences in terms of availability, performance and quality.

The takt time or planned cycle time can be a good target to strive for. If the operator walks away from the line to get a tray for parts and the machine shuts down, this prevents the shift from achieving the desired cycle time. Thus, more resources or overtime will be required to complete the job and deliver the product to the customer on time.

For example, in one factory an operator often left the machine to find tools or spare parts. Although the machine's uptime or availability was the full eight-hour shift, the operator's absence reduced the machine's actual use by 10 percent each shift. This company was subtracting the operator's absence from its calculation of effective operating time, thereby losing the opportunity to improve that process by better training and a better system for making sure that the operator had the right tools and parts.

OEE and improving capacity

Another powerful use for OEE is that it helps us find the bottleneck in the production process. A bottleneck is a machine or process that limits the production rate of the whole line. The bottleneck can be due to capacity or to unreliable performance.

Therefore, OEE does not just apply to a single process or single machine. OEE should be measured for various production processes and various machines in one line. OEE can be perfect but still limit production capability.

For example, take a production line that has one machine capable of delivering 100 units per hour sending its production down through a second machine that is capable of producing only 70 units per hour. The first machine will have to reduce its performance to match the capability of the second

machine. Thus, the first machine will produce 70 units an hour and have an OEE of 70 percent. The second machine will process the 70 units and have a perfect OEE of 100 percent, even though the second machine is the real bottleneck that limits productivity rates.

If all capacity improvement efforts have been exhausted in the above example, managers have a couple of options. They could add a third machine in parallel with the second one or replace the second machine completely. But managers could not have recognized such a problem without analyzing OEE and capacity for a series of machines in the production process. Such bottleneck machines could cause enormous losses if the sales losses are calculated over shifts, weeks, months and years.

Another good method for finding bottlenecks is to combine an analysis method like OEE along with a lean technique like mapping.

Building culture that assists improvement

The main goals of any organization are price, quality and delivery speed. OEE is a great tool for achieving these goals by improving productivity. OEE boosts the performance and the speed of the process as the metrics tend to look for all obstacles that prevent the process from achieving its targets. Results include lower costs, reduced use of scarce resources, better quality for customers, and smoother product flow to meet the customer takt time.

Companies that suffer from sales issues while increasing productivity rates likely will see no savings. The extra goods produced must be sold, or we just build inventory and increase costs. In such circumstances, use the extra free time to make further improvements or develop new products. Rather than producing unneeded inventory, this time can be filled with kaizens, searching for better ways to move material, solving other problems and improving quality.

In addition to policing adherence to new procedures and standards, training is important. All processes tend to slip back if the improvement made is not sustained and the employees have not been trained enough for the culture of continuous improvement and the frequent use of the plan-do-check-act cycle.

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